

WTG Manufacturer's Experience with Subsystem and Component Validation for Wind Turbines

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Abstract

Conventionally, wind turbine (WT) manufacturers are performing grid compliance tests at the WT level primarily in the field to verify the WT capabilities and performances against certain grid code requirements and validate simulation models accuracy and performance. Such compliance tests are becoming more challenging and numerous due to the growing number of relevant grid code requirements and the rapid growth of WT's size and rating, which in turn require more powerful test equipment and larger sites to test such turbines. Upcoming standards such as IEC 61400-21-4 and FGW AK KEZ and other industry initiatives aim to address these challenges through the replacement of site-specific tests with tests performed on WT components and subsystems in a controlled test bench environment. This paper presents the experience gathered so far on various test benches including nacelle, electrical generation, converter, and real time digital simulator test benches. The results of these different test benches brought important lessons regarding the transferability of the results through the evaluation and comparison with one another and benchmarking against site specific tests to assess their accuracy in representing the performance, capability, and functionality at WT level. Finally, a long-term grid compliance strategy, revolved around on moving part of the testing campaign to subsystem and component testing and modelling, is presented with a proposal of new test bench and acceptance strategies for the industry.

1 Introduction

The wind sector is evolving rapidly as society's demands for a more sustainable energy source have grown and are expected to continue growing for the upcoming decades with the need to quadruple by the end of the decade [1]. As a result of this, it can be expected that development and manufacturing procedures will need to be drastically improved in order for the industry to keep up with existing targets for net-zero emissions in the next decades.

In terms of grid compliance, since the early stages of the wind industry, wind turbines (WTs) have been primarily tested on site, also known as field testing. Typically field testing is performed on a prototype WT, where different types of tests are carried out including power quality, grid fault-ride through, protection, capability curves. Field testing is considered the benchmark when it comes to the highest fidelity possible, however, there are many challenges and drawbacks to solely relying on field testing for grid compliance assessment of WTs. The challenges include the growing complexity of testing requirements coming from grid codes and standards [2], challenges related to the dependency and unpredictability of weather conditions, Fault Ride Through (FRT) test container availability and increasing rating requirements, and other testing limitations when connected to the public grid. These challenges greatly impact the effectiveness of only using field testing for turbine grid compliance validation.

In addition to these technical challenges, the time available to launch new products, also known as "time to market", is gradually being shortened as the industry demands faster development cycles in an effort to continuously reduce the levelized cost of energy (LCOE). Therefore, it is prudent that alternatives to field testing are considered to address these challenges going forward.

Owing to this scenario, the testing strategies of the wind industry are currently undergoing changes towards a more modular approach where grid compliance testing of individual or multiple components and/or subsystems is performed on a test bench. At the same time, WT simulation models are becoming highly valuable in the development processes and validation of new WTs, as previously presented in [3, 4].

This paper presents the up-to-date manufacturer's experience with component and subsystem testing. In the following sections, an overview of the current state of component and subsystem standardization is given, followed by a presentation of the experience with various test benches and results. Finally, the future vision for the long-term grid compliance strategy is discussed by presenting a new test bench and discussing possible acceptance strategies for the industry. The experience presented in this paper is primarily based on Type 4 WTs.

2 Definitions of Component and Subsystem Testing

WT component and subsystem testing is characterized by a modular approach towards testing an entire system by subdividing it into components and/or subsystems. This approach has been proposed in several other industries (e.g. aerospace, vehicles, other sectors in power systems, etc) before and for different purposes depending on the objectives [5, 6]. The forthcoming IEC CD 61400-21-4 : Measurement and assessment of electrical characteristics - Wind turbine components and subsystems [7] and FGW guideline for component based unit certification [8] contains guidelines and definitions concerning test bench setups for subsystem and components testing. These standards aim to categorize various test bench types, which consequently determines the testing ability and applicable test scope of the test bench.

It is the opinion of the authors that test bench can be categorized into four general groups:

Type A - Nacelle Test Bench: This test bench includes the complete electrical system, either complete or partial mechanical drive train, and both the WT and converter control system. The mechanical drive train is connected to a prime mover to simulate the torque exerted by wind forces on the rotor. The electrical drive train is connected to a grid simulator to represent an external grid which can be actively controlled. The relevant nacelle auxiliaries are also included. Depending on the setup complexity it may include additional controller to simulate the wind field and dynamic forces on the mechanical drive train. This type of test bench is capable of complete testing both static and dynamic capabilities of the system as well as the functionality of the control systems.

Type B - Electrical Drive Train Test Bench: This test bench includes the complete electrical and WT and converter control system. The electrical drive train is connected to a prime mover to simulate the torque exerted by the mechanical drive train. The electric drive train is connected to a grid simulator to represent an external grid which can be actively controlled. Depending on the setup complexity it may include additional controller to simulate the mechanical drive train and the WT controller may be omitted. This type of test bench is suitable for testing static capability and control system functionalities, and depending on the setup complexity maybe be suitable for testing the dynamic capability.

Type C - Converter Test Bench: This test bench includes the WT converter, and WT converter control systems. The machine side of the WT converter is connected to a grid or a generator simulator and the grid side of the WT converter is connected to a grid simulator. Depending on the setup complexity it may include an additional controller to simulate the mechanical drive train, generator, and the WT controller may be omitted. The testing ability of this test bench is similar to that of the electrical drive train test bench depending on the setup complexity.

Type D - Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (cHiL) Test Bench: This test bench includes the WT and/or converter control system. The control system(s) are connected to a real

time digital simulator which simulates external components and subsystems and provides inputs to the control system being tested. The fidelity which such a setup simulates external subsystem (e.g. mechanical and electrical drive train) vary considerably. This test bench is suitable for testing control system functionalities.

It should be noted that these categories are not exhaustive and do not cover all test bench test type, they merely provide a summary of the most commonly used test benches for WT validation.

2.1 Types of Tests

The scope of tests which are to be performed as part of WT validation can vary in each market, although the IEC 61400-21-1 [2] provides a good reference for the types of tests which can be commonly required. In addition to industry standard type tests, new requirements are emerging for tests to validate additional aspects such as rate of change of frequency, phase jump, grid forming capability [9]. The validation of these tests can typically only be performed on a controllable test bench setup. An overview of some of the most common type tests and the experience regarding the respective minimum test bench ability required is listed in Table (1).

Test type	Minimum Test Bench ability
Harmonics	Static capability
Maximum power	Dynamic performance
Reactive power capability	Static capability
FRT performance	Dynamic performance
Grid protection	Functionality

Table 1 Overview of recommended minimum test bench ability based on test type

3 Test Benches and Methodologies

In this section, different test setups which were utilised are briefly described with a supporting diagram of the test setup. In all figures in this section, the continuous lines connecting the equipment denote power flow while the dashed lines denote communication between the equipment. Similarly, boxes with solid borders represent mechanical or electrical components, whereas boxes with dashed lines represent controller or simulated components. The majority of the communication, measurement, and control information are omitted in each figure for simplicity.

3.1 Field test setup

Figure (1) shows a generic single line diagram of a field test setup. A WT is connected to the public grid via a test unit used to apply short-circuit faults at the WT's medium voltage (MV) terminals. The point of common coupling is located at the MV side of the public grid transformer. Other tests such as Power Quality and reactive power capability do not require a test unit. Results from field tests should be considered the reference for comparison of other test setups in terms of fidelity, except in cases where field tests are not feasible.

Fig. 1. Field test setup.

3.2 Nacelle Test Bench - Type A

The Nacelle test bench allows for grid compliance testing of WT nacelles in terms of capability and performance. Figure (2) depicts the main components of the test setup including the WT complete nacelle, drive train (referred here as Prime Mover) powered by the test bench drive system to apply torque to the Device Under Test's (DUT) generator, and a grid simulator with MV converter to subject the DUT to various grid conditions and disturbances. The auxiliary systems and WT unit transformer were also integrated in the DUT setup. The grid simulator uses an open loop controller to regulate the grid voltage allowing for response times smaller than 5 ms. Furthermore, the wind field and WT mechanical drive train are simulated in real-time by a mechanical-hardware-in-the-loop (mHiL) simulator which provide the rotor speed references for the DUT [4].

Fig. 2. Nacelle test bench setup.

3.3 Full Power Converter Test Bench - Type B

The Full Power Converter Test (FPCT) bench consists of a WT converter connected in a back-to-back configuration to a three-winding transformer and grid emulator. A simplified block diagram of the FPCT bench is shown in Figure (3). This test bench can only be used for static capability tests due to its limited dynamic capability associated with such a back-to-back configuration.

Fig. 3. FPCT test bench setup.

3.4 Real-Time Digital Simulator Test Bench - Type D

The Real Time Digital Simulator Lab (RTDS) setup consists of a customized WT converter controller (DUT) to interface with RTDS I/O modules. A simplified diagram of the setup is shown in Figure (4). The laboratory test setup consists of the WT controller, a real-time simulator and a supervisory controller (monitoring). It should be noted that the mHiL rotor simulator was not implemented in the RTDS setup and only a simplified generator model was included, which can affect the performance of the results from this test bench.

Fig. 4. RTDS test bench setup.

4 Results

The results shown here are based upon measurements obtained in the test benches described in Section 3. The tests presented include grid protection, power quality - harmonics, fault ride through, and reactive power capability, where the tests were performed in accordance with applicable IEC standard [2, 7, 10–13].

4.1 Grid Protection

The grid protection test demonstrates the ability of the DUT to disconnect from the grid during abnormal voltage and frequency conditions. This test is performed by adjusting the measured voltage or frequency outside its respective protection threshold level until the protection system operates. Figure (5) shows results from field, RTDS, and FPCT test setup of the average time taken for the DUT protection system to send a trip signal upon exceeding the protection threshold. The DUT in each test setup succeeded in sending the trip signal with an

accuracy greater than 0.5% and 0.1% of the defined voltage and frequency protection trip level respectively.

Based on these results it can be stated that the FPCT approximately match the trip time and value of those from the field tests, where the largest deviation was found to be <8ms. The trip times observed in the RTDS measurements were found to be lower than the FPCT and field tests which can be attributed to fewer components included in the protection system chain (e.g. solid state relay) in the RTDS setup. The source of difference in the voltage and frequency protection clearing times of the RTDS results are expected to be caused by the difference in frequency and voltage calculation methods, although further investigation would be required.

Fig. 5. Average Protection Clearing Times.

It should be noted that the circuit breaker behavior and its inherent opening time delay is not included and a test of the whole protection system of the WT should still be carried out in field tests or alternatively the switchgear manufacturer provide a type test report demonstrating the opening time delay.

4.2 Power Quality - Harmonics

In Figure (6) the first graph shows the results of the 95th percentile harmonic voltages in the baseband range (below the first carrier group) for the RTDS, FPCT, nacelle/field tests. The second graph in (6) shows the corresponding mean average error (MAE) between the field/nacelle measurements and the RTDS and FPCT measurements. The power quality measurements on nacelle and field test setups were found to be equivalent and therefore are depicted together as a single set of results.

Except for the 3rd harmonic (which has low absolute voltage level) all results were within a MAE < 15% with max deviation in voltage below 0.15%. The characteristic odd harmonics (5th, 7th, 11th, 13th, etc.) and even the non-characteristic cluster of harmonics between the 22nd and 25th orders generally were in reasonable agreement with the nacelle/field measurements. Overall, the RTDS seemed to have smaller MAE than the FPCT. This is not surprising given that the FPCT had more harmonic sources which could distort the measurement (i.e. due to the gen-bridge and the grid simulator power converter).

Fig. 6. Comparison for Power Quality results.

4.3 Fault Ride Through (FRT)

In this section, the FRT results for two different voltage dips are presented; 1) a three phase (3ph) dip with 0% retained voltage and 2) a two phase (2ph) dip with 15% retained voltage. The same dips were replicated on the RTDS, nacelle and field test setup. All measurements presented here are taken at the low voltage terminals of the WT whilst the WT was delivering approximately rated power output.

Figure (7) includes graphs of the the positive sequence voltage, active power, and reactive current for a 3ph 0% voltage dip.

The **fault entrance** results of the RTDS and Nacelle test bench closely match the field measurement where steady state conditions are reached within 30ms. Differences in the peak reactive current of the test benches can be observed during this transient period (30ms), more notably in the nacelle test bench which may be a result of the dynamic control features of the grid emulator.

The **in-fault** measurements from each test benches match the field measurements with a high degree of accuracy in voltage, power, and current, where the RTDS is slightly less accurate possibly due to the lack of detailed mechanical and electrical models.

The **fault clearance** measurements from each test bench show significant differences when compared to field results. The main factor contributing to these differences can be attributed to the saturation effects of the WT transformer leading to slower recovery of the voltage. Such effects are not implemented in the RTDS, and effects of the transformer saturation in the nacelle test bench are mitigated through flux control feature of the grid emulator.

Figure (8) includes graphs of the the positive sequence voltage, active power, and reactive current, where Figure (9) includes graphs of the negative sequence voltage, and reactive current for a 2ph 15% voltage dip.

Fig. 7 Positive Sequence signals for a 3ph fault with 0% retained voltage.

The **fault entrance** performance of the nacelle test bench is superior in replicating the positive and negative sequence voltage, however, noticeable deviations can be identified in the positive sequence active power and reactive current during the transition period (30ms). The RTDS demonstrate higher accuracy in reproducing the negative and positive sequence reactive currents and has similar behaviour in active power.

The **in-fault** performance of the nacelle test bench obtains an accuracy in all variables of within 0.06 p.u.. Whereas the RTDS obtains a better match of the positive and negative reactive currents and larger deviations in the voltages and active power compared to the nacelle test bench.

Fig. 8 Positive Sequence signals for 2ph fault with 15% retained voltage.

During **fault clearance** the RTDS results show a significant overshoot of the positive sequence voltage and slower active power recovery. The slow active power recovery can likely be attributed to different parameter configuration used in this test case. Despite this, the accuracy of the positive and negative sequence reactive currents are relatively good. The nacelle test bench performs very well during fault clearance with only minor deviations in the positive and sequence reactive currents.

In general the in-fault performance of the RTDS and nacelle test bench accurately replicates the field setup. Minor deviations can be found in both test benches when examining the fault entrance performance. However, the most notable differences arise during the fault clearance which in some scenarios lead to deviations which are greater than 0.2 p.u.. The nacelle test bench is better able to reproduce the field behaviour in scenarios where the WT transformer saturation does not have a large impact on the voltage recovery (dependent on the clearance angle, remnant flux etc.).

Fig. 9 Negative Sequence signals for 2ph fault with 15% retained voltage.

4.4 Reactive Power Capability

This section examines the reactive power capability of the WT with respect to active power output or voltage level, also known as PQ curve or UQ curve respectively. PQ curve tests are performed by delivering maximum export/import reactive power whilst varying the active power output, whereas in UQ curve tests the voltage level is varied instead. Limitations arise during field tests performing either PQ or UQ curves tests as typically the grid voltage can not be controlled and is influenced by the active or reactive power output of the WT. A test bench with a grid simulator that can emulate a stiff grid, such as the nacelle test bench, is recommended for performing reactive power capability tests as it allows for accurate control of the voltage.

This section presents measurements performed on the field and nacelle test setup. Due to the voltage limitations mentioned above, it is not straightforward to directly compare field and nacelle results. For this reason the simulation was chosen as the reference for assessing the measurement deviation. It

is important to note that the simulation model represents the worst case scenario as it is parameterised using conservative tolerance values (e.g. transformer impedance) which typically underestimate the actual WT reactive power capability. This underestimation in the simulation model results is intentional as it ensures that a minimum guaranteed reactive power level can be achieved on all WTs in the field. As such, it is more appropriate to compare the relative error between nacelle and field measurements.

The deviation between measured and simulation for field and nacelle setup is shown in Figure (10). There is a good match between both measurement results for the import scenario. The field results for the export scenario significantly overestimate reactive capabilities and closer match between field and nacelle measurements are only obtained above 0.8 p.u. active power output levels.

Fig. 10 Nacelle and field PQ measurements deviation to simulation model.

4.5 Summary of Results

The results from test benches for various test types where compared against field tests in this chapter. The objective was to determine the ability of each test bench to accurately replicate field measurements. A summary for each test bench including their relative merits and drawbacks is given below.

RTDS: A wide scope of tests could be performed on the RTDS including FRT, Grid Protection and Power Quality. The results for these tests showed reasonable accuracy, however, the lack of detailed mechanical and electrical models limited its ability to properly reproduce the FRT performance in certain tests. The acceptance by external stakeholders of test reports prepared using the RTDS is assumed to be moderate and is not considered a substitute for field test cases. Despite these short comings, the RTDS can be considered relatively low cost, that can be readily adapted for new controllers.

FPCT: The FPCT test bench is very capable of performing static tests such as grid protection, voltage and frequency range, reactive power capability. However, due to the back-to-back configuration of the converters, the dynamic capability of this test bench is limited and is only applicable for type 4 WTs. Furthermore, the additional harmonic filters needed in

the test bench reduce the confidence in the harmonic results obtained on this test bench. The high costs of the FPCT due to the large rating of the grid simulator converter and transformer is not ideal, particularly considering its limited test scope and accuracy.

Nacelle: The nacelle test bench brings many benefits which are not offered by other test benches in terms of static capability and dynamic performance, test scope, and accuracy. It offers the closest substitute to field testing and brings with it a high level of confidence that the results closely match the WT performance in the field. Despite these strong advantages, there are drawbacks that can't be overlooked. Results obtained on this test bench do not necessarily align perfectly with field measurement as certain phenomena such as transformer saturation are mitigated through the flux control of the grid simulator or other differences in the grid conditions in the field compared to the test bench. Furthermore, the costs of a nacelle test setup are very high which is further compounded in the scenario that an existing test bench is outgrown with introduction of new and larger WT products.

5 Future Test-Benches and Validation Strategies

There is a strong incentive for WT manufacturers to transition towards a validation strategy which relies more on subsystem and component testing for the reasons described in Section 1. With this premise the salient questions are; 1) which combination of test setups should be used as part of WT validation and 2) the role which test bench results play in the overall WT validation process.

In answering the first question, many different factors determine the most suitable test setup including confidence in results, cost, scope of testing, time to market, acceptance by external stakeholders of test bench results towards validation, upgradability of test bench. In choosing a test bench the aim should be to optimise these factors to find the best overall solution which best fits the user and customer. A qualitative comparison of test benches examined is presented in Figure (11) based on different factors.

Fig. 11. Test Bench Qualitative Comparison

To overcome many of the challenges and drawbacks associated with the test benches examined in this paper it is proposed

to use a test bench setup referred to as Grid-Converter Test Bench (G-CTB) which can be classified as Type C according to this paper. This setup has both the WT converter and WT control system, which are then connected to separate inverter systems that simulate the generator and grid side as shown in Figure (12). The generator side simulator communicates with real time simulators of high fidelity models of the generator and mechanical components (mHiL controller) which include wind field effects on the WT. The grid simulator would utilise an inverter that possesses sub-millisecond latency control of the grid voltage along with other advanced features such as dynamic impedance emulation and harmonic injection. Reasons for omitting the physical generator and mechanical system would be the following:

1. The high fidelity models used in place of the missing physical components shall reproduce the expected behaviour with no significant loss in accuracy for the intended scope of tests.
2. The confidence and acceptance level of external stakeholders in the test bench results would be gained through extensive testing and comparison of test bench and field results. This comparison would demonstrate the fidelity of the test bench.
3. The removing physical components significantly reduces the costs and greatly improves the upgradability as additional inverter modules can be included to enlarge the power rating.

Fig. 12. Grid Converter Test Bench setup.

Based on the proposed capability of the G-CTB and for the reasons described above, it is argued that the G-CTB test ability would cover a wide scope of tests including harmonics, steady-state operation, dynamic & control performance, grid protection, and other non-standard tests such as df/dt , phase jump, and grid forming.

Considering the strong testing ability of the G-CTB, the principal question then becomes how bench tests results contribute towards WT validation. For certain test such as frequency capability the role of a test bench is clear as it is not viable to carry

out the test in the field. However, for other test such as reactive power capability or fault ride through, the role of a test bench in a WT validation strategy is not well defined. The most pressing points to be addressed in a validation strategy are which tests must be repeated in the field and transfer-ability of bench test results towards WT validation.

Given the continual improvement in test bench ability to replicate WT performance in the field, the question whether to continue performing such fielding testing gains legitimacy. Field testing will undoubtedly bring value in the form of identifying possible unforeseen issues, confidence and acceptance of test results, a baseline which to verify measurements obtained from a test bench among many other reasons. To ensure that test benches have a credible future, it is only appropriate that bench tests can substitute a significant portion of tests which would otherwise be performed in the field (e.g. half of FRT compliance tests performed in field tests, remainder on a test bench).

The proportion of tests which can be substituted is contingent on many factors. Transfer-ability refers to the ability bench tests can replace field tests which in general is dependent on the detail to which WT components & subsystems relevant to the electrical test are represented (real or simulated) and the fidelity of the test bench results with respect to field tests. These factors determine the less tangible aspects, yet equally important aspects, such as confidence and acceptance of test bench results which are not explicitly defined in standards, guidelines, or requirements e.g. specific tolerance to field measurements.

Furthermore, currently there are no guidelines for scenarios where test bench results deviate from field tests for the same test case. These scenarios can arise due to external effects only encountered during field testing (e.g. resonance with the external grid which impact harmonic results, transformer saturation impact on voltage recovery at fault clearance). These effects are very difficult to fully capture in a test bench setup, at the same time they do not invalidate the results obtained in the test bench, instead they represent the WT behaviour under a slightly different set of conditions for the same test case. The importance of this point should not be understated as it is not achievable to obtain a perfect match to field tests in any test bench, therefore it is imperative that the source of these deviations are well understood and verifiable. In these scenarios it is proposed to use an appropriate simulation model validated against field measurements to verify the correctness of the test bench results (i.e. open loop playback of measurements into model or closed loop model with detailed representation of test bench setup). In this sense the simulation model acts as a bridge to demonstrate the equivalency of the field and bench test results.

In order to gain confidence in a new test bench setup, the following validation strategy is proposed:

- (a) Perform comprehensive and thorough scope of tests on the test bench and field.
- (b) Validate simulation model against field test results.
- (c) Compare test bench and field tests to determine accuracy of test bench to reproduce WT behaviour in field tests.

- (d) Investigate source of deviation between test bench and field tests and use simulation model to verify source of deviation and prove equivalency.

Whilst this strategy creates additional effort in repeating the same test cases on both setups, this exercise shall create confidence in the test bench results and grow the level of acceptance with external stakeholders of the transfer-ability of bench test results. After the initial test campaign, subsequent test campaigns should seek to leverage the strengths of a proven test bench and shrink the scope of field tests.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, the main motivations for the partial/full transition from field testing to the use of test benches to validate WT component and subsystem was discussed followed by a generic definition of different test bench types, ranging from Types A and D. Furthermore, the experiences with test benches of Types A, B and D were presented in a more detailed manner accompanied by a comparison and assessment of the test benches results of various test types against field measurements.

It could be concluded that the Nacelle test bench (Type A) offers the closest substitute to field testing with a high level of confidence, however certain phenomena could not be reproduced in the bench as well as cost and scalability limitations are factors that can hinder the benefits of this type of test bench. Results from FPCT test bench (Type B) showed that it can be very capable of performing static tests, however due to the configuration presented, its scope of tests is limited and are accompanied by high costs of implementation. Finally, results from the cHiL RTDS test bench (Type D) showed to be reasonably accurate and with low cost, however, due to the lack of additional electrical or mechanical HW/SW, this type of test bench can be limited in reproducing the dynamic performance of the WT and therefore are likely to not be widely accepted by external stakeholders.

Drawing on the experiences gathered thus far, the main challenges and gaps going forward were defined and summarized with the proposal of a future test bench G-CTB (Type C) and validation strategy to ensure an optimal test bench setup and overall acceptance by external stakeholders.

7 Legal Disclaimer

Figures and values presented in this paper should not be used to judge the performance of Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy technology as they are solely presented for demonstration purpose. Any opinions or analysis contained in this paper are the opinions of the authors and not necessarily the same as those of Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy.

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